

Arithmos Is Not Enough For Economics
Part II: Freedom or Plasticity May

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ertuğrul İbrahim KIZILKAYA
University of İstanbul
Faculty of Political Sciences

Abstract

In search of a more proper *eidōs* for economics, some valuable thoughts of philosophers like Sartre and Hegel may be helpful. Catherine Malabou's approach of *plasticity*, inspired by Hegel, provides the potential to bring an important expansion to economic thought by pointing to the freedom of human beings and their ability to take shape or continuous metamorphose and giving form or the power to create a new human life. This is the unique ability of human being, named as *autourgike* in the context of Plato's thought. For economics, where a limited conceptualization and an intense mathematical formalism dominates, as in the *homo economicus* typology, it would be appropriate to explore human plasticity and freedom, creativity or the contingencies that arise in this process, instead of focusing on facts based on an unchanging human essence.

Keywords: *arithmos, eidōs, homo economicus, freedom, plasticity.*

Introduction

The scope of mainstream economics is the study of the relations between man and matter. The human being alienated from nature, in the process of coming to his own consciousness, started to see nature as a substance, a resource or an opportunity; and in the context of the survival instinct, he tended to instrumentalize the nature. The law of insoluble contradiction between unlimited needs and scarce resources or *scarcity* which is included in the generally accepted definition of economics by Lionel Robbins, is a modern interpretation of the process in question. In fact, man, who first created a subsistence economy, had gained superiority over nature in time and has been chasing power and wealth in the so-called market economy. Therefore, as a social science, economics is focused on producing the knowledge of the relationship plane that emerged in the context of human historical drift. The knowledge of obtaining optimal economic power and using this power is investigated, under the scarcity law constraint. The typology of man in this research area is *homo economicus*. In line with the understanding of the human being who alienates from nature and builds a life for himself and with his own hands by instrumentalizing nature, the typology in question assumes an essence, a nature or a substance about human beings. The accepted essence for *homo economicus* is rationality.

However, the acceptance of man's rationality is not wrong, but at least an incomplete starting point. The defense of many economists against such objections generally focuses on emphasizing that this starting point is the most appropriate methodological tool. Again, it is of course impossible to oppose human rationality, and the rationality assumption can be accepted as an appropriate methodological tool. However, approaching the complex structure of human life through this assumption alone limits the perspective of economics. As a matter of fact, the science of economics, which approaches the reality from a limited perspective or through a distorted consciousness, tends to repeat itself on the one hand, and on the other hand, gives weight to formalism in order to preserve its scientific appearance. The increasing need to develop new conceptual perspectives on human beings is being tried to be met by statistical, econometric and similar quantitative methods.

In this article, this approach will be discussed based on Plato's concepts of *eidōs* and *arithmos*. Plato, one of the most important philosophers of the ancient age, is perhaps one of the most basic sources to be consulted for appropriate answers to the questions that are wanted to be answered, with his important contributions to each of the concepts needed to think. After examining his thought, the argument that Plato's *eidōs* on human being may be inadequate, will be discussed by approaching from a different angle, even if Plato's emphasis on human *eidōs* is appropriate. In this context, the second important perspective discussed in this article is to question which concept can be applied as an alternative *eidōs*, by referring to the concepts of important figures of the history of philosophy.

Freedom as the Eidos of Existence and Human Being

Plato's thought helped us to realize that *arithmos* alone could not provide the ultimate knowledge of man. Plato drew attention to the need for an *eidos* when we wanted to bring together the information we reached with *arithmos*. However, while Plato was guiding us through the dualism of *eidos* and *arithmos*, he also pointed out that there is a final understanding of *eidos* about human beings. *Philosophos*' journey and finally his contemplation of the truth would lead to a *theoria* of the *eidos* in question. However, as emphasized in the lines above, it is necessary to leave this thought and question the possibility of a new *eidos*. Therefore, it would be appropriate to focus on this problematization now.

If a person has the *autourgike* feature, if he is able to create himself, if he is able to build very different lives for himself, there is a need for questioning and original concepts in this direction. If it does not have a given essence, it exists first and then builds the essence of its own existence, it would be appropriate to consider human beings through a creative understanding of freedom. As can be expected, the approach of Jean Paul Sartre in *Being and Nothingness* can help us here:

“Man is free because he is not an itself but self-presence. A being that is what it is cannot be free. Freedom is precisely the nothingness that *is been* at the heart of man and which obliges human-reality to *make itself*, rather than *to be*. As we have seen, for human-reality to be is *to choose itself*: nothing comes along from outside—or from inside, either—for it to *receive* or *accept*. Human-reality is entirely abandoned, without help of any kind, to the unbearable necessity of making itself be, right down to the last detail. In this way freedom is not *a* being: it is man's being, i.e., his nothingness of being. If we conceived man in the first instance as a fullness, it would be absurd to seek afterward within him for moments or psychological regions where he might be free: we might as well look for a gap inside a container that we have previously lled right up to the rim. Man cannot be sometimes free and sometimes a slave: he is free in his entirety and always, or he is not.” (Sartre, 2018: 625)

Sartre's lines define man as total freedom. To put it using the concept of *eidos*: man does not have an *eidos* of freedom to share. Similar to Plato's definition of *dikaion* not as an attribute of *anthropos psukhe*, but as its *eidos*, Sartre considers freedom not as one of human qualities but as its *eidos*.¹ This is such an *eidos* that compels one to do oneself; here again, to be expressed with a concept used by Plato. However, the said *autourgike* feature should not be thought of as a pre-planned holistic process; it has no beginning, no stages of development and no final destination. On the contrary, it should be regarded as a kind of adventure that will never end:

“The meaning of realism, naturalism, and materialism lies in the past: these three philosophies all describe the past as if it were present. The for-itself is therefore a twofold flight from the world: it escapes its own being-in-the-midst-of-the-world as presence to the world from which it flees. The flight's free and final term is the possible. The for-itself cannot flee toward something transcendent that it is not but only toward a transcendent that it is. This is what removes any possibility of there being an end to this constant flight. If I may use an image that is somewhat demotic—but helps to capture my thought—I would remind the reader of the donkey pulling a cart behind him, trying to catch a carrot that someone has fixed to the end of a stick, which is in turn attached to the shafts. Every attempt made by the donkey to catch the carrot has the effect of moving the harnessed cart forward in its entirety—along with the carrot itself, which remains always at the same distance from the donkey. In this way, we run after a possible that is brought into view precisely by our running—a possible that is nothing other than our running, and which by that very fact is determined as being out of reach. We are running toward ourselves and we are, in consequence, the being that

¹ In another article, starting from Kant's Thought, I've tried to express the ethos of freedom of mankind (or freedom as the *eidos* of mankind), with the following lines: “Indeed, the original potential of man is the ability to complete the deficiencies and thus his original creative nature. When Kant wanted to point it out, he was talking about the concepts of freedom and morality. Thus, instead of being limited to the instrumental rationality of a heterologous homo phainomenon (economics), it would be possible for an autonomous homo noumenon to set goals for himself and establish a unique ethos.” (Kızılkaya, 2020: 152)

cannot ever be reunited with itself. In one sense, our running lacks any meaning, since its final term is never given but invented and projected even as we run toward it. And, in another sense, we cannot withhold from it the meaning that it rejects, since, despite everything, the possible is the for-itself's meaning. Instead, our flight has — and has not — meaning.” (Sartre, 2018: 338-339)

In that case, the person who is free with the *autourgike* feature is making himself, in other words, he is escaping from his own present. However, this escape is not towards a transcendence, to *aletheia*, as in Plato. Unlike this, human is beyond his current existence. Human is a creature that escapes from himself and runs towards himself again. If its distinctive feature is freedom, this freedom is bold steps towards an undetermined future in the present. This courage is to invent oneself while making (building) oneself. Therefore, according to Sartre, human progresses by not being what he was in the past and what he is now, or, in his famous expression, human existence precedes his essence:

“Through it, the for-itself escapes from its being, as from its essence; through it, the for-itself is always something other than what we can say about it, because it is at the least that which escapes this very naming, which is always beyond the name we give to it, beyond the property we acknowledge it to have. To say that the for-itself has to be what it is, to say that it is what it is not by not being what it is, and to say that existence precedes and conditions its essence, or vice versa, and according to Hegel's formula, that in its case “*Wesen ist was gewesen ist*,” is to say one and the same thing: namely, that man is free.” (Sartre, 2018: 623-624)

As Sartre emphasized, the essence of man for Hegel is what has become. This essence does not exist as an immanence in man, nor is it given by transcendence. Therefore, the essence of man is not given, unchangeable, and therefore does not have a unity to be discovered through various methods.² The essence of man cannot be mapped, because it cannot yet be said to have emerged in the context of time and space. In the world in which he was launched, within the scope of the interactions created by external conditions, man builds new lives as himself and for himself. Itself is freedom:

“In these conditions, since any event in the world can be disclosed to me only as an opportunity (an *opportunity* that can be *put to use, missed, neglected*, etc.) or, better still, since we can regard everything that happens to us as a chance — which is to say it can appear to us only as a means of actualizing this being that is in question in our being — and since others, as transcended-transcendences, are, in their case too, only *opportunities* and *chances*, the for-itself's responsibility extends to the world in its entirety as a peopled-world. That is precisely how the for-itself apprehends itself in anguish, i.e., as a being who is the foundation neither of its being nor of the other's being, nor of the in-itselfs that form the world, but who is forced to decide on the meaning of being, within him, and everywhere outside of him. Someone who actualizes, in his anguish, his condition of *being* thrown into a responsibility that stretches back even to his abandonment no longer has any remorse, or regret, or excuse; he is no longer anything but a freedom which is absolutely disclosed to itself, and whose being resides in this very disclosure. But most of the time, as we pointed out at the beginning of this book, we flee from anguish in bad faith.” (Sartre, 2018: 764)

² At this point, it would be appropriate to draw attention to another existential approach: “Being a self, Da-sein is the thrown being as self. Not through itself, but released to itself from the ground in order to be as this ground. Da-sein is not itself the ground of its being, because the ground first arises from its own project, but as a self, it is the being of its ground. The ground is always ground only for a being has to take over being-the-ground.” (Heidegger, 1996: 262) According to Heidegger, human is an entity that came from nothing and was thrown into the world. Its orientation is also death, hence nothingness; therefore, man is a finite being. The essence of man, who is left between two nothings, is his existence, and the essence in question is nothingness. This essence has not been determined. So, for Heidegger, Dasein is not just an existent that exists in the world (in-der-Welt-Sein), but an existent by projecting itself towards the future being-possibility. This existence, called *ek-sistenz*, is the exit from in-der-Welt-Sein or everydayness towards Being. Dasein, turning to Being, throws itself into the future possibility of being. To put it another way, man has the freedom to reconstitute himself in the context of future possibilities. Dasein, on the one hand, is finite, on the other hand, as a being of possibility, it is transcendental and in this respect free. It is free because it does not derive its transcendence from a transcendent, its transcendence is in itself. For Heidegger, Being is existence opened to the future.

As can be seen in these long quotations from Sartre, the fact that man is a creature that makes, constructs and invents himself should again be the main problematization to which human thought should be directed. Transforming the human behaviors that emerge on the *doxa* plane into data, making the mystery of human beings the subject of research with the *dianoia* activity to be carried out on them with the *arithmos* dimension, is an incomplete effort, even if it is not wrong. What such a vision will provide to human beings will still be limited, and will even pave the way for struggles that are now stuck. However, there is no route to be determined by starting from the past and no purpose to be dealt with from now on. Man will establish all these starting from today and only after that. If a rationality is to be sought, we can find it in the founding mind (objective mind), which boldly constructs the future, rather than the functional mind (or instrumental mind) that is stuck in the present. It would be appropriate to search for another important thinker, Hegel, for the conceptualization that can help in the questioning in this direction.

Hegel and Plasticity

Hegel considers the liberation of man by getting rid of the necessities of nature as a historical process. In other words, the transformation of nature through man and the liberation of man within the scope of this transformation and the realization of a harmonious sociality are considered as a process of civilization. This comprehensive process has been directed by human thought and given its content. Hegel frequently refers to the concept of Spirit (*Geist*) while talking about these processes, changes and transformations. In this context, it can be said that, according to Hegel, man is both the subject and the object of history. To put it differently, human is on the one hand active, but at the same time the product of his own activity. So, one of the most important questions that can come to mind is the conceptualization of the human essence:

“Human beings are truly human through consciousness-by virtue of the fact that they think and by virtue of the fact that they are spirit. This gives rise to manifold images and configurations, i.e., the sciences, the arts, political interests, the relationships that are connected with human freedom and will.” (Hegel, 1984: 113-114)³

Those who think that the essence of man needs to be discovered and those who make abstractions in search of establishing a system (*theoria* in the modern sense, not Platonist), leave out the elements related to historicity or sociality, and replace the gap regarding the essence of man and his behavior with their own patterns. However, there is no definitive criterion on how to determine this essence. Hegel, on the other hand, thinks that man produces himself in his own historical drift, creates himself and represents himself to himself through contingencies that are his own product. The statements in Hegel’s book *Reason in History* reveal this situation:

“After the creation of nature appears Man. He constitutes the antithesis to the natural world; he is the being that lifts itself up to the second world. We have in our universal consciousness two realms, the realm of Nature and the realm of Spirit. The realm of Spirit consists in what is produced by man. One may have all sorts of ideas about the Kingdom of God; but it is always a realm of Spirit to be realized and brought about in man.” (Hegel, 1953: 20)

Human being, which produces itself in this world, in other words, is both the subject and the object of this process, is one of the *sui generis* pinnacle of rationalist and idealist thought:

“Man is no longer a living creature like others; ill reflecting upon his life he immediately finds himself on the margin of this life, he grasps it as a risk, as the necessity of death. He confounds

³ Hegel also pointed out the possibility of failure of this task: “The hollow object which it generates to itself it thus now fills only with the consciousness of emptiness. It is a yearning which only loses itself as it becomes an essenceless object, and as it goes beyond this loss and then falls back on itself, it only finds itself as lost. – In this transparent purity of its moments it becomes an unhappy, so-called beautiful soul, and its burning embers gradually die out, and, as they do, the beautiful soul vanishes like a shapeless vapor dissolving into thin air.” (Hegel, 2018: 380-381)

himself with nature from which he emerged and yet from which he is separate; the life instinct and the death instinct are, as it were, the poles of an irresolvable dualism. This is the source of alienation and the origin of the problem of human destiny.” (Hyppolite, 1969: 87-88)⁴

In that case, the person who accepts his destiny in the world will tend to build his own life and will assign himself a mission in this direction. In *The Future of Hegel*, Catherine Malabou claims that we can read Hegel’s conceptualization through his concept of *plasticity*:

“The dialectical process is ‘plastic’ because, as it unfolds, it makes links between the opposing moments of total immobility (the ‘fixed’) and vacuity (‘dissolution’), and then links both in the vitality of the whole, a whole which, reconciling these two extremes, is itself the union of *resistance* (*Widerstand*) and fluidity (*Flüssigkeit*). The process of plasticity is dialectical because the operations which constitute it, the seizure of form and the annihilation of all form, emergence and explosion, are contradictory. The connection linking the three concepts, ‘Plasticity’, ‘Temporality’, and ‘Dialectic’, now becomes clear: it is nothing less than the *formation* of the future itself.” (Malabou, 2005: 12)

From today’s perspective, future human life is a reconstruction that will occur in the context of human abilities. Malabou uses the conceptualization of *voir venir* (to see what is coming) to discuss this process:

“‘Voir venir’ in French means to wait, while, as is prudent, observing how events are developing. But it also suggests that other people’s intentions and plans must be probed and guessed at. It is an expression that can thus refer at one and the same time to the state of ‘being sure of what is coming’ (‘être sûr de ce qui vient’) and of ‘not knowing what is coming’ (‘ne pas savoir ce qui va venir’). It is on this account that the ‘voir venir’, ‘to see (what is) coming’, can represent that interplay, within Hegelian philosophy, of teleological necessity and surprise.” (Malabou, 2005: 13)

So, in Hegel’s thought, the life built by man extends from today to tomorrow, is embodied in a dialectical relationship and has a *plastic* feature. It is not possible for us to have the teleology that will enable us to know in advance what this future will be like. On the other hand, it would be misleading to claim that we can never know how the same future will take shape. There is a continuous change in the dialectical process of beings, towards a moment that is not yet known. To paraphrase this point in Malabou’s words:

“Self-determination is thus the relation of substance to that which happens.” (Malabou, 2005: 12)

Also this *self-determination* is *plasticity*:

“Plasticity refers to an equilibrium between the receiving and giving of form. It is understood as a sort of natural sculpting that forms our identity, an identity modeled by experience and that makes us subjects of a history, a singular, recognizable, identifiable history, with all its events, gaps, and future.” (Malabou, 2012a: 3)⁵

⁴ At this point, starting from Heidegger, the idea that the motif that drives people to creativity is anxiety (angst) in the face of death can be problematized. The context of these and similar motifs not being able to carry people into the context of *autourgike* or moving away from the ability of human beings to build human life is expressed as the everydayness of *Das Man* (ordinary person) in Heidegger, while in Hegel *ein sich in sich bewegendes Leben des Toten* (life of the dead moving within itself) is met with the expression. In this context, it can be said that a person who loses his *autourgike* feature (ability and/or possibility) descends to the level of *automaton* (machine or robot).
⁵ Malabou points to different possibilities of plasticity: “The term ‘plasticity’, one should recall, has three principal significations. On one hand, it designates the capacity of certain materials, such as clay or plaster, to receive form. On the other hand, it designates the power to give form—the power of a sculptor or a plastic surgeon. But, finally, it also refers to the possibility of the deflagration or explosion of every form—as when one speaks of ‘plastique,’ ‘plastic explosive,’ or, in French, *plastiquage* (which simply means ‘bombing’). The notion of plasticity is thus situated at both extremes of the creation and destruction of form.” (Malabou, 2012b: 17) Also: “Recalling Hegel’s use of plasticity to describe the true nature of the relationship between subject and predicate, Malabou argues that plasticity characterizes the relationship of substance and accident.” (Lynch, 2019: 128) Malabou also highlights the difference between flexibility and plasticity: “To be flexible is to receive a form or impression, to be able to

According to Malabou, human *plasticity* as a *motor scheme* will play a very important role in the future as it does today:

“In the light of what I have said, it should be clear that plasticity refers to both a new mode of being of form and a new grasp of this mode of being itself, in other words, a new *scheme*. ...[P]*lasticity is the systemic law of the deconstructed real*, a mode of organization of the real that comes after metaphysics and that is appearing today in all the different domains of human activity. In *Le Change Heidegger*, I tried to define this new configuration as *an ultrahistorical configuration of the world, a mode of transformation following history*. Today, *new metamorphic occurrences* are appearing at the level of social and economic organization and at the level of “gender” or individual sexual identity.” (Malabou: 2010, 57)⁶

It can be emphasized that this approach of Hegel is in harmony with Sartre’s claim that human existence comes before essence. First of all, the existing human will then build his own essence. In the context of the interaction of this essence with external conditions, the life into which man is born (also called *politeia* or social life) will be created. Here, the concept of *plasticity* in Hegel refers to more than one ability of the human being at the same time. Accordingly, a conscious person can both shape and take shape. If it is approached from another angle, while a person repeats himself in his life, which is his own product in some periods, he can also change, develop and progress in other periods.

At this point, it should be emphasized that sometimes human *plasticity* can cause its unexpected excesses. Even if it cannot get out of *Doxa*’s illusion, it can create a sudden and unexpected event. However, this spontaneous event and other events that can be attributed to a meaning cannot be said to be happening for a purpose. Therefore, the point to be focused on is not emphasizing that people are moving towards a goal that was determined from the very beginning, but rather the dynamics within which the process in question takes place in a dialectical manner. So, instead of looking for a transcendent or immanent *arkhe* for the lives that people have established and are building for the future, it would be appropriate to bring this mutual relationship to light.⁷ One can continue to ponder on a transcendent purpose or the unfolding of an immanent nature. However, it is useful to add the

fold oneself, to take the fold, not to give it. To be docile, to not explode. Indeed, what flexibility lacks is the resource of giving form, the power to create, to invent or even to erase an impression, the power to style. Flexibility is plasticity minus its genius.” (Malabou, 2008: 12) Similar distinctions are found in Sigmund Freud: “One can thus postulate that, for Freud, there are two plasticities within plasticity: constructive plasticity and destructive or mortiferous plasticity. In *Beyond the Pleasure Principle*, Freud writes, citing the biologist Ewald Hering: “According to E. Hering’s theory, two kinds of processes are constantly at work in living substance, operating in contrary directions [entgegengesetzte Richtung], one constructive or assimilatory [die einen aufbauen—assimilatorisch] and the other destructive or dissimilatory [die anderen abbauend—dissimilatorisch].” He affirms that these two directions allow us to recognize “both of our instinctual impulses, the life drives and the death drives.” Each drive would be assigned its own physiological process: either construction (Aufbau) or decomposition (Zerfall).” (Malabou: 2012b, 172)

⁶ In the Introduction of *The Heidegger Change: On the Fantastic in Philosophy* Malabou named as W, W, & V and discussed Heidegger’s concepts of changes (Wandeln), transformations (Wandlungen), and metamorphoses (Verwandlungen). (Malabou, 2011, 1-30)

⁷ At this point, a discussion can be developed over the concept of anti-materialist metaphysical argument put forward by Saul A. Kripke. For Kripke, “rigid designators” fully grasp what they refer to in all possible worlds. (Kripke, 2001: 3-15) Within the framework of this thesis, it can be said that human beings exist in all possible worlds with the same physical characteristics, or the name human is a rigid designator for the same creature. However, it is historical within the framework of the world we live in, to grasp the living thing called homo economicus, in other words, the bond that man establishes with matter, through the rationality postulate, and to define it as an optimization unit that pursues self-interest. Put differently, this historical definition need not be valid in all possible worlds. The name homo economicus, then, is not strictly indicative, but perhaps historical-social-institutional. While constructing his own contingent world, man has added something non-physical (social, institutional, historical) to his physical/biological life in such a way as to create the said change. This extra contribution can be conceptualized as founding reason (or freedom or Plasticity) in the context of Kripke’s anti-materialist metaphysical argument.

perspective of orientation towards the reciprocal, continuous, dynamic and cyclical relations between the *autourgike* ability of the human being and the external conditions he faces.⁸ Man carries himself and his environment towards his future. The nature of his creativity and destructiveness is contained in this unsolved interaction.

Conclusion

A common point of different interpretations of existential thought is, in this context, the ability of man to construct and/or transform himself. From this perspective, man cannot be explained performatively over a given *eidos*. It can be said that no final schema or map of man can be drawn through research on the *eidos* in question. In other words, the essence of man should not be seen as a given principle but rather as an open-ended ability. Sartre expressed this phenomenon as a human running from himself to himself. Heidegger's approach is slightly different: according to him, man exists by opening himself up to future possibilities. Hegel, on the other hand, reveals that man both takes form and shapes human life. In this context, Malabou emphasizes that Hegel points to human *plasticity*. In the context of a certain temporality, human transforms, liberates and realizes progress through transcending, including both his life that contains contradictions and his external conditions, like a dynamical and continuous *metamorphosis*.

Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the perspective of orientation towards the mutual, continuous, dynamic, dialectical and cyclical relations established between the external conditions of human life and the human *autourgike* ability. Instead of focusing on facts based on an unchanging human essence, it would be appropriate to explore human freedom, creativity and the contingencies that arise in this process. In the context of economics, it should be considered to make room for concept and thought partnerships with other disciplines of humanities in the field where a limited conceptualization and an intense mathematical formalism dominate, as in the *homo economicus* typology.

Bibliography

- Heidegger, Martin. *Being and Time*, (New York: State University of New York Press, 1996).
 Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Reason in History*, (Indianapolis: Bobs-Merrill Co.: 1953).
 Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Lectures on the Philosophy of Religion, Volume I: Introduction and the Concept of Religion*, (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1984).
 Hyppolite, Jean. *Studies on Marx and Hegel*, (New York: Basic Books, 1969).

⁸ Although it is the subject of a future comprehensive study, Quentin Meillassoux's ideas, the important name of speculative materialism, can be examined in this context. Meillassoux points to human's unsurpassability: "The appearance of humans in the World of thought is by no means an accident, because humans are named as the realisation of this capacity. Having nothing to do with a particular biological make-up, for Meillassoux the human is a being that can grasp its contingent existence in relation to the absolute truth of contingency, the realisation of this unsurpassable relationship. The human is accorded a special place in factual ontology, for ex nihilo novelties are specified by the fact that they define it. The emergence of the next World, which Meillassoux argues will be the World of justice, is complicated by the unsurpassability of the human: as a World it must involve some form of ex nihilo novelty that further defines the human, but this novelty is barred from being an addition which would exceed the World of thought. This complication leads Meillassoux to suggest that the World of justice would entail the immortality of humans as its ex nihilo novelty." (Neylan, 2015: 78) Meillassoux point out, for the human, the importance of "may-be" (peut-être) instead of "be" (être): "For the may-be unites within itself the true heart of every ontology (the absoluteness of factual possibility) and the deepest aspirations of ethics (the universal fulfillment of justice)." (Meillassoux, 2010: 463) If the world that Meillassoux called the fourth world of justice (the other three ex nihilo worlds marks respectively the essential ruptures of becoming: matter, life, and thought) could have an effect on the present existence, there will be a vectorial subject motivated by the desire for universal justice. With this solution, it is hoped that divine inexistence will free the vectorial subject from the negativities of arbitrary violence and frustrations. Christopher Watkin addresses Meillassoux's attitude as supreme human value meets anti-anthropocentrism: "It is in relation to the modalities of the advent of this fourth world that Meillassoux speaks of the divinisation of the human: 'To be deified is to turn oneself into a demon: a metaxu, an intermediary, a living passage between the thinking of this world and the justice of the ultimate world'." (Watkin: 2016, 51)

- Kızılkaya, Ertuğrul. "Positive Economics From the Perspective of Kant's Thought", *Examining the Relationship Between Economics and Philosophy*, ed. İlkben Akansel, chapter 7, 145-159, (Hershey PA: IGI Global, 2020).
- Kripke, Saul A. *Naming and Necessity*, (Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press, 2001).
- Lynch, Thomas. *Apocalyptic Political Theology: Hegel, Taubes and Malabou*, (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2019).
- Malabou, Catherine. *The Future of Hegel: Plasticity, Temporality and Dialectic*, (London: Routledge, 2005).
- Malabou, Catherine. *What Should We Do with Our Brain?*, (New York: Fordham University Press, 2008).
- Malabou, Catherine. *Plasticity at the Dusk of Writing: Dialectic, Destruction, Deconstruction*, (New York: Columbia University Press, 2010).
- Malabou, Catherine. *The Heidegger Change: On the Fantastic in Philosophy*, (New York: State University of New York Press, 2011).
- Malabou, Catherine. *Ontology of the Accident: An Essay on Destructive Plasticity*, (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2012a).
- Malabou, Catherine. *The New Wounded: From Neurosis to Brain Damage*, (New York: Fordham University Press, 2012b).
- Meillassoux, Quentin. "The Immanence of the World Beyond", *The Grandeur of Reason: Religion, Tradition and Universalism*, eds. Peter M. Candler, Conor Cunningham, 444-478, (London: SCM Press, 2010).
- Neylan, Fintan. "Fourth World of Justice", *The Meillassoux Dictionary*, eds. Peter Gratton, Paul J. Ennis, 77-79, (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2015).
- Sartre, Jean Paul. *Being and Nothingness: An Essay in Phenomenological Ontology*, (New York: Washington Square Press, 2018).
- Watkin, Christian. *French Philosophy Today: New Figures of the Human in Badiou, Meillassoux, Malabou, Serres and Latour*, (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2016).